

MEDICAL SCIENCES

STRESS COPING STRATEGIES IN PATIENTS WITH PSYCHOSOMATIC DISORDERS AND THE NURSE'S ROLE IN STRESS REDUCTION

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Abstract

Stress is a significant factor affecting both psychological and physical health, often manifesting as psychosomatic symptoms without a clear organic cause. In hospital inpatient settings, stress-related psychosomatic disorders may complicate treatment, prolong recovery, and worsen health outcomes. However, the integration of stress management into nursing care remains insufficiently developed.

The aim of this study was to determine stress coping characteristics among patients with psychosomatic disorders and to evaluate the nurse's role in reducing patients' experienced stress. A quantitative descriptive study was conducted using an online questionnaire. The final sample consisted of 332 respondents who had been treated in hospital inpatient departments. Data were collected using the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS-10), the Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-15), and an adapted Brief COPE questionnaire, and analyzed using statistical methods.

The results showed that psychosomatic symptoms were mostly of low to moderate severity, with fatigue, sleep disturbances, headache, and dizziness being the most common. A significant association was found between higher stress levels and stronger psychosomatic symptom expression. Longer hospitalization was also related to increased symptom severity.

Patients emphasized the importance of both personal involvement and nursing support in coping with stress. The nurse's role was identified as multidimensional, including emotional support, information provision, motivation, and communication. The findings highlight the need for a holistic, patient-centered approach integrating stress management into nursing practice to improve patient outcomes.

Keywords: psychosomatic disorders; stress coping; nursing role; patient stress; inpatient care; stress management

Introduction

In contemporary healthcare, stress has emerged as a pervasive and multifaceted phenomenon with significant implications for both psychological and physical health outcomes. It is commonly defined as the body's response to internal or external stressors, which may be physical, emotional, or psychological in nature [9]. Increasing evidence suggests that prolonged or intense exposure to stress contributes to the development of psychological disturbances that frequently manifest through somatic symptoms, including pain and other bodily complaints without a clearly identifiable organic cause [4, 7]. These manifestations are conceptualized as psychosomatic disorders, which represent a growing concern in modern clinical practice.

Patients with psychosomatic disorders, particularly those receiving inpatient care, often experience complex and reciprocal interactions between psychological distress and physical symptomatology. The co-occurrence of psychological and somatic conditions has been shown to exacerbate disease severity, prolong recovery, and negatively affect treatment outcomes [10, 6]. Furthermore, research indicates that psychosomatic manifestations are influenced by sociodemographic and health-related factors, including gender and age, with women and older individuals demonstrating increased vulnerability [12]. These findings highlight the

necessity of adopting a holistic and patient-centered approach in healthcare, where both psychological and physical dimensions are addressed concurrently.

Despite the increasing recognition of psychosomatic disorders in scientific literature, their assessment and management in clinical settings remain insufficiently developed. Psychosomatic symptoms are frequently underestimated or overlooked, leading to fragmented care and suboptimal treatment outcomes [3]. Moreover, patients experiencing stress-related psychosomatic symptoms often report more severe physical complaints, slower recovery, and poorer treatment outcomes compared to those without psychological distress [1, 8]. However, the integration of stress management strategies into routine nursing care remains inconsistent, and there is a lack of systematic, evidence-based approaches to addressing these symptoms in everyday clinical practice [11,2].

In addition, patients frequently tend to deny or underestimate the psychological origins of their physical symptoms, which limits their engagement in stress reduction interventions and complicates the provision of holistic care [5]. This creates additional challenges for nurses, who must not only recognize psychosomatic manifestations but also effectively involve patients in the management process. Consequently, a clear research gap emerges, highlighting the lack of empirical evidence on how patients with psychosomatic disorders cope with stress and what specific nursing interventions

are most effective in reducing patient-experienced stress.

Within this context, the role of nurses is particularly critical. As frontline healthcare providers maintaining continuous contact with patients, nurses are uniquely positioned to identify psychosomatic symptoms, assess stress-related factors, and implement targeted interventions aimed at reducing patient stress. Strengthening nurses' competencies in stress management and psychosomatic care is therefore essential to improving patient outcomes and ensuring high-quality, holistic care.

Against this background, the aim of this study is to determine stress coping characteristics among patients with psychosomatic disorders and to examine the role of nurses in reducing patients' experienced stress. The object of the study is stress coping in patients with psychosomatic disorders and the nurse's role in stress reduction. To achieve this aim, the following objectives were formulated: (1) to analyze stress coping strategies among patients with psychosomatic disorders, and (2) to evaluate the measures applied by nurses to reduce patients' experienced stress. A quantitative research design was employed, using a questionnaire survey as the primary data collection method, and the collected data were analyzed using statistical analysis techniques.

Research Methodology

A quantitative descriptive cross-sectional study design was employed to investigate stress coping among patients with psychosomatic disorders and the role of nurses in reducing patient-experienced stress. The study was conducted following a structured research process, including the formulation of the research aim and questions, development of the research instrument based on scientific literature, data collection, statistical analysis, and interpretation of results.

Participants and Sampling

A non-probability purposive sampling method was applied in this study. The inclusion criteria comprised individuals who had been treated in a hospital inpatient department, were able to understand Lithuanian, and voluntarily agreed to participate. A total of 360 respondents participated in the survey; however, after excluding incomplete or invalid questionnaires, 332 responses were included in the final analysis. The participants represented a diverse age group ranging from under 29 to over 60 years. Sociodemographic variables analyzed included gender, age, education, employment status, and marital status. Only respondents who had experienced hospitalization were included in the final dataset.

Data Collection

Data were collected using an online questionnaire administered via the platform apklausa.lt. The survey link was distributed through social media (Facebook) in order to reach a broader population and ensure accessibility. This method was selected due to its efficiency and ability to collect data from a large number of respondents within a relatively short period of time. Data collection was carried out from September 27 to November 18, 2025, with repeated sharing of the survey link to increase response rates.

Measures

The research instrument consisted of four structured sections. The first section included sociodemographic questions (7 items) designed to collect general information about the respondents. The second section applied the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS-10), which consists of 10 items rated on a 5-point Likert scale and demonstrated acceptable internal consistency in this study (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.796$). The third section included the Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-15), used to assess psychosomatic symptoms, with 15 items rated on a 3-point Likert scale and high internal reliability (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.860$). The fourth section utilized an adapted version of the Brief COPE questionnaire, consisting of 30 items, to evaluate stress coping strategies and the role of nursing-related support. All instruments were publicly available and used in accordance with academic research requirements.

Data Analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS software (version 27.0.0). Data distribution was assessed using the Shapiro-Wilk and Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests, which indicated that most variables did not meet the assumptions of normality. Therefore, non-parametric statistical methods were applied. The Mann-Whitney U test was used for comparisons between two groups, the chi-square (χ^2) test with Fisher's exact correction was applied for categorical variables, and Spearman's rank correlation coefficient (ρ) was used to assess relationships between variables. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Ethical Considerations

The study was conducted in accordance with fundamental ethical principles, including voluntariness, anonymity, confidentiality, and respect for human dignity. Participants were informed about the aim of the study and their right to withdraw at any stage without any consequences. No personal identifying information was collected, ensuring full anonymity of the respondents. All data were used exclusively for research purposes and handled in accordance with established ethical research standards.

Manifestation of Psychosomatic Symptoms During Hospitalization in an Inpatient Department

The Patient Health Questionnaire-15 (PHQ-15) was used to assess psychosomatic complaints. It was found that in the overall study group, the mean total score of psychosomatic complaints out of a possible 30 points was 8.32 ± 5.82 , indicating that, on average, respondents demonstrated a low to moderate level of psychosomatic symptom severity. Analysis of the distribution of respondents according to the level of psychosomatic symptom manifestation showed that, for the majority of participants, somatic symptoms during hospitalization in the inpatient department were absent or only mildly expressed. A minimal level of psychosomatic symptom manifestation was identified in 31.3% of respondents, a low level in 29.8%, a moderate level in 21.1%, and a high level in 17.8%. Thus, it can be stated that more than half of the respondents experienced minimal or low psychosomatic symptom severity; however, nearly one-fifth of the participants

demonstrated a high level of symptom manifestation. When evaluating the frequency of individual psychosomatic symptoms, the results showed that the most common symptoms experienced by respondents during hospitalization, particularly in states of stress or anxiety, were fatigue or lack of energy (69.3%), sleep disturbances (67.5%), headache (64.2%), dizziness (54.9%), and gastrointestinal problems such as constipation, bloating, or diarrhea (48.5%). Cognitive dysfunction was reported least frequently, being observed in only 8.7% of respondents. These findings suggest that stress experienced during hospitalization was most strongly associated with general physical discomforts that are commonly characteristic of psychosomatic reactions.

Analysis of the associations between the level of psychosomatic symptom manifestation and sociodemographic characteristics revealed a statistically significant relationship with age ($\chi^2=25.74$; $p=0.012$). A high level of psychosomatic symptom manifestation was significantly more frequent among respondents younger than 30 years compared to older age groups. A statistically significant relationship was also found between the level of psychosomatic symptoms and employment status ($\chi^2=9.59$; $p=0.022$). Employed respondents more frequently belonged to the minimal or low psychosomatic symptom groups, whereas unemployed respondents more often demonstrated moderate or high symptom severity. No statistically significant differences were found according to gender, education, or marital status ($p>0.05$).

The results further revealed that a higher level of psychosomatic symptom manifestation was significantly associated with a longer duration of hospitalization in the inpatient department ($\rho=0.17$; $p=0.002$). In addition, a moderate positive correlation was found between psychosomatic symptom manifestation and perceived stress during hospitalization ($\rho=0.44$; $p<0.001$), indicating that greater perceived stress was associated with more severe psychosomatic symptoms.

Analysis of the associations between individual psychosomatic symptoms and stress levels showed that stronger manifestation of all evaluated symptoms was statistically significantly associated with higher perceived stress ($\rho=0.11-0.38$; $p<0.05$). The strongest correlations were found between stress and fatigue or lack of energy ($\rho=0.38$; $p<0.001$), chest pain or pressure ($\rho=0.35$; $p<0.001$), stomach pain ($\rho=0.33$; $p<0.001$), headache ($\rho=0.32$; $p<0.001$), nausea or digestive problems ($\rho=0.32$; $p<0.001$), dizziness ($\rho=0.31$; $p<0.001$), palpitations or heart rhythm disturbances ($\rho=0.31$; $p<0.001$), sleep disturbances ($\rho=0.31$; $p<0.001$), and bowel-related problems ($\rho=0.30$; $p<0.001$). The weakest, though still statistically significant, associations were found for pain in the arms, legs, or joints, cognitive dysfunction, and memory impairment. These findings suggest that stress experienced during hospitalization is particularly associated with general physical discomfort and autonomic bodily reactions.

Stress Coping Among Patients Suffering from Psychosomatic Disorders and the Role of the Nurse in Reducing Patients' Experienced Stress

The study sought to identify which stress coping strategies and forms of nursing support, in the respondents' opinion, would be most helpful in reducing stress or anxiety during hospitalization in an inpatient department. For this purpose, respondents were presented with 30 statements related to stress coping strategies and the nurse's role, which were rated using a 4-point Likert scale.

The findings demonstrated that respondents placed greatest importance on the patient's active involvement in the recovery process and cooperation with nurses. The highest-rated statement indicated that the patient should take action to improve the situation and follow the nurses' instructions (3.11 ± 0.97). Other highly rated stress coping strategies included engaging in non-strenuous activities suggested by the nurse in order to think less about the problem (2.92 ± 1.00), receiving information from the nurse about physical exercises that help reduce stress (2.88 ± 1.06), learning to live with the illness and seeking nurses' advice regarding one's condition (2.87 ± 0.98), as well as becoming involved in activities that help distract thoughts from the problem (2.83 ± 1.09). These results indicate that respondents considered both personal effort and professional nursing support to be important.

The findings also revealed that, in the respondents' opinion, the nurse's role in stress reduction is multifaceted. Important nursing functions included providing information about physical exercises for stress reduction, informing other specialists about the stress experienced by the patient (2.82 ± 1.07), motivating the patient, offering emotional support, engaging in more frequent communication, and maintaining open conversation. Respondents also emphasized the need for emotional support from nurses (2.67 ± 1.12), receiving comfort and understanding (2.66 ± 1.01), and obtaining advice or help on how to cope in stressful situations (2.65 ± 1.02). These data suggest that the nurse's role in patient stress management encompasses not only informational and organizational functions, but also emotional and motivational support.

The least effective stress coping strategies, according to respondents, were refusing nursing assistance and attempting to cope with stress independently (1.79 ± 0.93), as well as denying the situation and ignoring nursing support (1.54 ± 0.88). This indicates that patients were more likely to acknowledge the importance of nursing support than to rely solely on isolation or denial.

When analyzing gender differences in stress coping evaluations, several statistically significant differences were identified. Men significantly more often than women indicated that they would benefit from the use of technologies such as virtual reality or augmented reality by nurses ($p=0.005$). In contrast, women significantly more often than men expressed a preference for receiving information from nurses about physical exercises that help reduce stress ($p=0.043$), and they more frequently emphasized the importance of receiving nurses' advice regarding their illness ($p=0.026$). These findings suggest that men's and women's expectations of nursing support in stress management may differ.

Analysis according to marital status revealed that respondents who had a partner significantly more often than single respondents stated that stress was reduced by self-motivation and motivational support from nurses ($p=0.040$), by seeking comfort in religion or spiritual beliefs with the support of the nurse ($p=0.025$), and by learning to live with the illness while receiving advice from nurses about their condition ($p=0.026$). In contrast, no statistically significant differences were found in stress coping strategies according to employment status ($p>0.05$).

Correlation analysis revealed that younger respondents were significantly more likely than older respondents to actively engage in stress coping and to expect greater support from nurses. Younger age was associated with a greater tendency to take action to improve the situation, follow nurses' instructions, seek emotional support and motivation from nurses, expect more frequent contact, request assistance in distracting thoughts from problems, hope for permission to use a phone or computer, and desire the opportunity to listen to relaxing music. In contrast, higher educational attainment was associated with a greater need for emotional support, permission to use technologies, the provision of suitable conditions for prayer or meditation, and the inclusion of homeopathic methods in the nursing process. A longer duration of hospitalization was associated with higher perceived effectiveness of certain nurse-provided interventions, particularly non-strenuous activities, informing other specialists, listening to relaxing music, the application of virtual or augmented reality technologies, and motivational support.

The results also showed that higher perceived effectiveness of nearly all stress reduction strategies was statistically significantly associated with higher levels of perceived stress and psychosomatic symptom severity. The strongest associations were found between greater stress and psychosomatic symptom severity and the desire to receive emotional support from nurses ($\rho=0.43$; $p<0.001$ and $\rho=0.35$; $p<0.001$, respectively), as well as self-criticism and the wish to be left alone or transferred to a single room ($\rho=0.40$; $p<0.001$ and $\rho=0.37$; $p<0.001$, respectively). Significant associations were also identified with the desire for information from nurses about physical exercises, communication with other specialists, more frequent nurse visits, the opportunity to listen to music, conditions for prayer or meditation, the inclusion of homeopathic methods, and the application of technological solutions for stress reduction.

On the other hand, some stress coping strategies were not dependent on the level of perceived stress or psychosomatic symptom severity. These included taking action to improve the situation and following nurses' instructions, as well as receiving help and advice from nurses on how to calm down. In addition, the evaluation of receiving comfort and understanding from the nurse, engaging in non-strenuous activities, and learning to live with the illness while seeking advice about one's condition did not depend on perceived stress severity. This suggests that some coping strate-

gies may be perceived by patients as universally beneficial regardless of the intensity of stress or psychosomatic symptoms.

Conclusions

The findings of this study demonstrate that stress coping among patients with psychosomatic disorders in inpatient settings is primarily based on active and adaptive strategies, including engagement in self-directed actions, cooperation with nursing staff, distraction through non-strenuous activities, and cognitive acceptance of the situation. A statistically significant association was identified between higher levels of perceived stress and increased severity of psychosomatic symptoms. The most prevalent symptoms included fatigue, sleep disturbances, headache, and dizziness, with symptom severity increasing alongside longer hospitalization duration and higher perceived stress levels.

The role of nurses in reducing patient-experienced stress is essential and multidimensional, encompassing informational, emotional, motivational, and coordinative functions. Patients particularly value the provision of clear information, emotional support, ongoing communication, and the involvement of other healthcare professionals. The results indicate that as stress and psychosomatic symptom severity increase, so does the demand for individualized care and emotional support from nurses. These findings highlight the importance of implementing a holistic, patient-centered, and individualized approach in nursing practice to effectively manage stress and psychosomatic symptoms in inpatient care settings.

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